

Editorial

The Sacredness of Creation

īśā vāsyamidam sarvam yatkiñca jagatyām jagat
tena tyaktena bhuñjīthā mā ḡrhaḥ kasyasviddhanam

All this, whatever moves in this universe (and that those move not), is covered (indwelt or pervaded) by the Lord. That renounced, enjoy. Do not covet anybody's wealth (Ishavasya Upanishad).

The universe is a dwelling place of God, and the creation manifests God's glory and presence. God is immanent within the created world, sustaining and permeating all existence. The pervasive presence of the divine in creation often leads to a sense of reverence, awe, and interconnectedness with the sacred.

The sacredness of creation underscores a deep respect and awe for the natural world, often rooted in religious or spiritual beliefs. It can inspire a sense of responsibility towards the environment and a commitment to preserving the earth for future generations. The sacredness of the creation emphasizes the reverence and respect for the planet as a living entity deserving of protection and care. This perspective transcends religious boundaries and is often associated with ecological, environmental, and spiritual beliefs. The natural world is sacred because it deserves deep respect and protection due to its inherent value, biodiversity, and role in sustaining life. Embracing the sacredness of the creation often involves adopting a holistic perspective that considers the well-being of the entire ecosystem. This goes beyond human-centric views and recognizes the intrinsic value of all living beings and the creation itself.

Indigenous cultures, in particular, often revere the earth and the interconnectedness of all living things, considering the land, water, and other natural elements sacred. The earth is seen as a living entity deserving of reverence, and traditional practices are often centered around maintaining harmony with nature. This interconnected web underscores the idea that

harming the environment affects all life forms, including humans. Those who view the creation as sacred often see themselves as stewards with the duty to protect and preserve the environment for future generations.

The sacredness of the creation often inspires a set of environmental ethics that guide individuals and communities in their interactions with nature. This can include sustainable practices, conservation efforts, and a commitment to reducing environmental impact. This perspective encourages a sense of awe and gratitude for the natural world, fostering a deep connection with the environment. The sacredness of the creation invites us to have a deep appreciation for the planet and a commitment to preserving its health and vitality for the benefit of present and future generations.

The Bible emphasizes the divine origin of the world, the goodness of creation, and the responsibility of humanity to care for and steward the Earth (Gen 1-2). God reveals himself through his creation (Pss 19:2-5; 33:8; Isa 55:11, etc.) and ensures that his creation will not perish as he loves the creation (Wis 11:26), and his spirit is in all things (Wis 12:1). God speaks, and the universe comes into existence (Gen 1; Pss 33:6-7; 148:5-6). God defeats the forces of chaos and disorder that threaten human existence and establishes peace in the creation (Pss 74:12-17; 89:9-10; Isa 27:1; 51:9-11; Hab 3:2-15). Whenever the hostile forces break forth, God would destroy them (Pss 24:1-2; 93:1-4; Isa 51:9-11). God is “good to all, and his compassion is over all that he has made” (Ps 145:9). The goodness of God revealed in creation a profound motivation to praise God (Pss 104:35; 147:1,8-9; 148:1-14; Job 38-41). God judges the oppressors of the creation and restores it (Isa 41:17-20; 42:5-9; 43:1-3; 44:24-28; 54:9-10).

The creation texts in the Old Testament also underscore God’s providential care for the creation. God’s care for creation did not stop at the time of creation, but assures of continued care: assures the succession of the seasons (Gen 8:22), care for the earth, food for humans and animals, dwellings for the birds (Ps 104:10-15; Gen 1), joy and comfort (Pss 104:14-16; 147:5-9). The joys of food and drink, rest, sexuality, etc., are all a part of God’s care for human life (Prov 5:15-20; Eccl 2:24; 3:13; 9:7-9 etc.).

Although God originally intended creation to be good, man’s selfishness and greed disfigured the creation. Yet one day these will be removed, and creation will be characterized by harmony, peace, and the knowledge of God (Isa 11:6-9), and the nations, now alienated from the God

of Heaven, will rejoice in Yahweh's goodness and justice (Isa 42:4; 51:5; 52:10), and become one with the people of God (Isa 19:25; Zech 2: 11).

In short, the sacredness of creation in the Bible forms the basis for many religious teachings on environmental ethics and the moral imperative to protect and cherish the natural world. Caring for the environment is a crucial aspect of responsible and sustainable living. It involves adopting practices and making choices that minimize negative impacts on the natural world, promote conservation, and contribute to the well-being of the planet.

Pope Francis has been a prominent advocate for environmental stewardship and care for the planet. In 2015, he released an encyclical titled *Laudato Si'* (Praise Be to You), and in 2023, an apostolic exhortation entitled *Laudate Deum* (Praise God). Both documents address the interconnectedness of ecological, social, and economic issues. He emphasizes the interconnectedness of all aspects of creation, including human beings, the environment, and social justice. He calls for an integral ecology that recognizes ecological, economic, and social well-being relationships. While he acknowledges the scientific consensus on human-induced climate change, he urges global cooperation to address this urgent issue. He calls for responsible stewardship of the earth's resources and reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

Pope Francis critiques the throwaway culture and excessive consumerism contributing to environmental degradation. He encourages individuals and societies to adopt a more sustainable and mindful approach to consumption. Moreover, he emphasizes the need for global solidarity to address environmental challenges. He advocates for international cooperation and responsibility to ensure the well-being of the entire planet and all its inhabitants. He underscores the intrinsic value of nature and the importance of respecting and protecting the environment as a sacred gift. He calls for a renewed sense of awe and wonder at the beauty of the natural world.

Pope Francis stresses the importance of ecological education in fostering a sense of responsibility and care for the environment. He encourages dialogue between different sectors of society, including scientific, political, religious, and cultural communities, to promote the "care for our common home." He also highlights the role of faith communities in environmental stewardship. He calls on religious leaders and followers to

actively care for the earth, viewing environmental protection as a moral and spiritual imperative.

In short, both *Laudato Si'* and *Laudate Deum* significantly impacted discussions surrounding climate change and environmental ethics. Pope Francis continues to be a vocal advocate for environmental issues, using his position to raise awareness and inspire action on a global scale. His teachings underscore the moral responsibility to care for the environment and promote a more sustainable and just world.

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